

HIGH TEMPERATURE BEHAVIOR OF PPS-BASED COMPOSITES FOR AERONAUTICAL APPLICATIONS: INFLUENCE OF FIRE EXPOSURE ON TENSILE AND COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIORS

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ABSTRACT

The influence of fire exposure on the high-temperature residual tensile and compressive behaviors of carbon fibers woven-ply Polyphenylene Sulfide (PPS) has been investigated. For heat fluxes ranging from 20 to 50kW/m², a fire exposure appears to be more detrimental to compressive mechanical properties than to tensile ones, as the residual strengths decrease by 80% and 30% respectively. By means of SEM observations, it appears that melting and resolidification (during cooling) of the PPS matrix due to fire exposure influence the post-fire properties by changing the meso- and micro-structures. In fire-exposed laminates, the thermal decomposition of the PPS matrix leaves intra- and inter-laminar voids which may act as preferential sites for delamination during tensile loading, and to plastic buckling during compressive loading. Once the melting temperature is reached (280°C) during fire exposure, the melted PPS matrix is redistributed within the carbon fibers network which ultimately maintains a partial cohesion, hence justifying that high-performance TP-based laminates maintain a high degree of retention of residual tensile properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

A major disadvantage of many composite materials is poor performance in fire, which is of the utmost importance for applications in aerostructures [1]. The behavior of polymer composite materials in fire has been a major concern for over thirty years, and much effort has been devoted to investigating their fire behavior and assessing their residual mechanical properties [2]. The International Aircraft Certification (IAC) requires fire resistance certification of aircraft composite materials [3], used in civil aircraft exterior structure and engine compartments (e.g. engine nacelle). The engine nacelle encases the jet engine compressor, combustors, and turbine. A nacelle fire is typically a turbulent diffusion flame stabilized behind an obstruction in a moderately high speed air flow [4]. It usually results in a heat release rate, which is the amount of thermal energy released by a material per unit area. The heat release rate can be determined at small scale using a sample exposed to an electrical heater radiating a constant heat flux.

In Polymer Matrix Composites (PMCs), the heat from a fire may weaken the polymer and cause eventual creep and structural failure as the temperature exceeds the glass transition temperature. Alternatively the polymer itself may ignite and spread the flame, releasing further heat and potentially toxic smoke. The behavior of polymer composite materials under fire conditions has been the subject of many investigations concerning the fire-induced degradation and the residual post-fire mechanical properties [2]. On the one hand, it is well established that the reduction to the post-fire mechanical properties of thermosetting (TS) laminates is due to thermal degradation and damage caused by fire. On the other hand, it is observed that thermoplastic-based composites (TP) generally have higher decomposition temperatures, yield high amounts of char, and are less susceptible to delamination cracking than TS laminates [2]. As a result, TP-based composites usually have higher post-fire

properties, but the mechanical behaviors of thermally degraded TP-based composites are still not well understood, particularly when they are considered for high temperature applications [5,6]. In addition, behavior under compression is clearly the Achilles' heel of composite behavior under load in fire [7,8].

High performance thermoplastics (TP), such as Polyphenylene Sulfide (PPS) and Polyether ether ketone (PEEK) are known to yield high amounts of char provided the heat flux is high enough to lead to the onset of pyrolysis [2]. Char, also known as non-fuel fraction, results from the thermal decomposition of organic resins. It is a highly porous material that can consist of crystalline and/or amorphous regions [2]. Thermal degradation processes which occur within PPS laminates have been studied by Montaudo et al [9]. From the fire performance standpoint, the basic idea of the present work is to find out whether it is relevant to replace thermosetting-based (Epoxy) composites by TP-based (PPS) composites for aeronautics purposes (nacelles of aircraft's engines), or not. The service temperature of these nacelles is 120°C, hence justifying to perform tests at $T > T_g$ for C/PPS. To meet certification requirements, it is therefore necessary to evaluate how detrimental a prior fire exposure can be on the residual tensile and compressive behaviors of PPS-based laminates. In order to investigate the fire-induced mechanisms, a fractography analysis was performed by means of SEM observations.

2 MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Materials and specimens

The composite materials studied in this work consist of 7 plies carbon fabric-reinforced PPS prepreg laminate plates [5,6]. The semi-crystalline PPS resin (Fortron 0214) is supplied by the Ticona Company. The woven-ply prepreg, supplied by the SOFICAR Company, consists of 5-harness satin weave carbon fiber fabrics (T300 3K 5HS), with a mass fraction of fibers of 58%. The prepreg plates are hot pressed according to two stacking sequences: quasi-isotropic and orthotropic [± 45]₇.

2.2 Experimental set-up and methods

Most studies dealing with the fire behavior of PMCs use the radiant cone heater to burn laminate specimens [2]. The advantage of this test is that the heat flux and heating conditions are well-controlled and repeatable. However, the cone calorimeter can only burn small specimens and exposure to a cone heater represents an idealized fire condition: the heating rate and final temperature are stable and there is no convective heat transfer from the heat source to the specimen. Four heat fluxes (20 – 30 – 40 – 50 kW/m²) have been applied to the materials for different exposure times (1 – 2 – 5 min).

After fire-exposure, all the specimens were cooled in the air for one night. The “virgin” state chosen for comparison purposes represents the state of specimens exposed to no prior fire. Five specimens were tested in each configuration. In order to explain the damage mechanisms, an analysis based on fractography observations was performed using an optical microscope Olympus. SEM investigations were also performed on LEO 1530 microscope.

DSC tests were carried out on virgin and fire-damaged specimens to determinate the degree of crystallinity by using a Perkin Elmer DSC7. Five samples were randomly taken from laminates, and for each batch (8-10mg), the temperature program consisted in holding the temperature for 2min at 30°C followed by a heat up from 40°C to 320°C at a rate of 10°C/min.

Thermal decomposition was investigated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) in different atmospheres using a Netzsch TGA 209 device. Parallelepiped samples of 10 mg (± 2 mg) were cut from areas of laminates exposed to fire. Measurements were performed under oxygen and nitrogen with a constant heating rate of 10 K/min and flow rate of 35 ml/min.

Once the specimens have been exposed to a given fire condition, thermo-mechanical testing was performed using a 100kN capacity load cell of an MTS 810 servo-hydraulic testing machine to determine their residual properties. The temperature control system includes an oven and a temperature controller, and the tests temperature was 120°C. Tensile tests were conducted on specimens with both stacking sequences. The tensile properties were determined according to the

standards [10,11]. Compressive tests were conducted only on quasi-isotropic samples, whose geometry was initially developed for compression after impact testing (Fig. 1). The specimen is placed within a special fixture originally designed by Boeing, which incorporates adjustable side plates to accommodate for both variations in thickness and overall dimension, as well as to prevent specimen buckling. Such a compression after impact fixture is placed between the compression platens of the testing machine. These specimens were therefore subjected to compressive loadings at a constant displacement rate $V=0.2\text{mm/min}$, complying with the standard Airbus AITM 1-0010 [12].

Figure 1: Compression after fire tests – Experimental set-up and anti-buckling fixture

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fire exposure tests

During fire exposure, temperature was monitored at the exposed surface of the specimens by means of thermocouples, in order to measure the temperature increase at the exposed surface due to the heat flux (Fig. 2a). As temperature increases, the first mode of fire-induced failure for C/PPS laminates is associated with the viscous softening of the PPS matrix around its T_g . At higher temperatures, the second failure mode is matrix decomposition due to the pyrolysis of the polymer matrix. The thermal decomposition of polymers usually involves interacting chemical and physical processes, producing both volatile combustible (black smoke) and incombustible products as well as char [9,13]. During exposure to the heat flux, no dripping of the PPS matrix out of the composite specimens occurred even for the highest heat fluxes (e.g. 50kW/m^2). In addition, specimens have not ignited when tested at the different heat fluxes.

Figure 2: Influence of fire conditions:

(a) Surface temperature – (b) Degree of crystallinity by means of DSC scans

In PPS-based laminates, the influence of fire on the meso-structure does not significantly depend on the applied heat flux [6]. For heat fluxes ranging from low to high (e.g. $20\text{-}50\text{ kW/m}^2$), the meso-structure of fire-damaged laminates is similar from the macroscopic scale standpoint (Fig. 3). On the edges of the exposed areas, the thermal decomposition of the PPS matrix in laminates' matrix-rich areas leaves intra- and inter-laminar voids which may act as preferential sites for delamination. The

matrix undergoes a series of reactions resulting in a redistributed melted matrix within fibre reinforcement, which is salient to maintain a good cohesion of the fibrous reinforcement, and is expected to be reflected in the residual properties of laminates. The presence of carbon fibers therefore modifies the heat transfer and the temperature distribution through the thickness, and limits the mass transfer of the PPS matrix out of the laminates.

Figure 3: Microscopic and SEM observations of edges in quasi-isotropic laminates: (a) Virgin laminates – (b) Specimen subjected to 20kW/m² for 2min

Fire-induced damages occur in different zones throughout the laminates, and variations in polymer matrix content in the in-plane and through-thickness directions can be observed. At the laminates' surface of compressive test specimens, a fire exposure due to a cone heater leads to circular damaged zones, whose area linearly increases as heat flux increases (Fig. 4a). At high heat flux, damage expands along the free-edges of the laminates (Fig. 4b). Through the thickness, damages extend below the hot surface in zones termed the char region, decomposition region, and virgin region [2].

Figure 4: Influence of fire conditions on the fire-damaged area of compressive test specimens: front and free-edge views

3.2 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

The glass transition temperature of C/PPS is $T_g=98^\circ\text{C}$, and its melting temperature is $T_m=280^\circ\text{C}$ [14]. The degree of crystallinity χ was determined by means of DSC tests, and was calculated using the following equation:

$$\chi = \frac{\Delta H}{\Delta H_{100\%} \times (1 - m_f)} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where ΔH is the measured enthalpy from the melting peak, $\Delta H_{100\%}$ is the enthalpy of melting of a theoretical 100% crystalline polymer (150.4 J/g) and m_f is the fiber mass fraction of the composite. The degree of crystallinity of this material (semi-crystalline polymer) gradually decreases from 25 to 0% as heat flux increases from 20 to 50kW/m² (Table 1). Depending on fire testing conditions, the crystalline phase represented by the melting peak on DSC curves tends to disappear (Fig. 2b).

Testing conditions	Virgin	20kW/m ²	30kW/m ²	40kW/m ²	50kW/m ²
Degree of crystallinity [%]	26.69 ±1.76	24.52 ±0.94	22.83 ±1.11	13.19 ±0.68	0

Table 1: Influence of heat fluxes on C/PPS laminates' degree of crystallinity

3.3 Thermogravimetric analysis

In order to investigate the thermal degradation kinetics of PPS-based laminates at a constant heating rate, TGA tests have been performed. The thermal degradation of the polymer and subsequent mass loss can be observed more specifically under a nitrogen atmosphere, as the degradation of carbon fibers is limited in inert atmospheres.

Figure 5: Thermal decomposition of C/PPS laminates under O₂ and N₂:
(a) Weight vs temperature – (b) Derivative of weight vs temperature

The TGA measurements performed provide the residual mass fraction vs. temperature curves, which reveal two-step decomposition in C/PPS laminates (Fig. 5a). In the first decomposition step, random chain scission is believed to be the main mechanism, whereas the second decomposition step is attributed to the oxidation of the carbonaceous char formed as a result of the first decomposition step. Char is instrumental in retaining the fire structural properties of composites [15-17]. The onset of thermal degradation under nitrogen occurs at $T_d \approx 500^\circ\text{C}$, and significant mass loss occurs (about 20%) between 500 and 600°C (Fig. 5), the remaining mass fraction appears to be carbonaceous char [15]. The char yield is defined by the mass fraction of carbonaceous char that remains after flaming

combustion of the polymer [1]. TGA tests performed on fire-damaged specimens under N_2 show that when the matrix has already been severely degraded due to prior fire exposure, the subsequent thermal decomposition of the matrix by TGA is limited (Fig. 5a). These additional tests were aimed at investigating how detrimental the fire exposure on the thermal decomposition of the matrix, and more importantly how it may change the value of the estimated char. In C/PPS laminates, the temperature at the maximum fuel generation are virtually the same and the thermal degradation kinetics are function of the fire exposure (Fig. 5b).

Figure 6: Comparison of tensile responses at 120°C depending on prior exposure conditions: (a) Quasi-isotropic – (b) $[\pm 45]_7$

3.4 Post-fire thermo-mechanical testing

After they were exposed to different fire conditions, the specimens have been subjected to tensile or compressive loadings at 120°C. From the obtained results, it appears that the influence of fire exposure on the thermo-mechanical behavior and properties depends on both stacking sequence and on the type of loading (Fig. 6 and Fig. 8). From the thermo-mechanical behavior standpoint, at temperatures higher than T_g , the PPS matrix softens, the matrix/fibre interface weakens and PPS-based laminates (both quasi-isotropic and $[\pm 45]_7$) lose much of their stiffness and strength (Tables 2,3,4). In order to better understand the influence of matrix on post-fire tensile properties, the fiber – or matrix-dominated mechanical responses of laminates have been investigated by means of quasi-isotropic or $[\pm 45]_7$ stacking sequences.

Figure 7: SEM observations of carbon fibres surface in C/PPS laminates subjected to 40kW/m² heat fluxes

In Q-I laminates, the 0° oriented fibers bear most of the load (73% according to the classical laminates theory), and the laminate response is dominated by the behavior of these 0° fibers. Thus, the tensile response is virtually elastic/brittle for all the fire conditions despite the highly ductile behavior

of the PPS matrix at high temperature (Fig. 6a). In addition, the tensile mechanical properties decrease more or less depending on the fire conditions (Tab. 2). In order to evaluate the influence of fire conditions, these properties have been compared to the values of the virgin materials (without prior fire exposure). A change in the fire exposure time from 2 to 5min at low heat flux (e.g. 20kW/m²) does not affect the properties of quasi-isotropic laminates. At high heat flux, the decrease in both stiffness and strength is about 30%. Once the melting temperature is reached during fire exposure, the melted PPS matrix is redistributed within the carbon fibers network which ultimately maintains a partial cohesion. Re-melted PPS matrix is also expected to protect the carbon fibres against oxidation in C/PPS laminates during fire exposure (Fig. 7), hence resulting in a relatively high degree of retention (70% of the virgin material) of residual tensile properties after fire exposure.

In A-P laminates, the matrix-dominated response results in elastic-ductile behavior for both composite systems (Fig. 6b). The nonlinear behavior of fiber-reinforced polymer composites becomes significant around their T_g , especially under off-axis loading conditions. With respect to the virgin materials, the shear modulus and ultimate strength decrease significantly (about -50%) after fire exposure. From the microscopic observations of fire-damage laminates (Fig. 3b), it appears that both inter- and intra-laminar areas are severely degraded, resulting from the formation of voids which may act as preferential sites for delamination during tensile loading. These changes in the laminates meso-structure significantly modify the in-plane shear behavior as it the load transfer between plies is reduced.

		Virgin	After fire exposure			
			20kW 2min	20kW 5min	35kW 2min	50kW 1min
E_x	[GPa]	40.49 ±0.30	33.33 ±0.56 (-18%)	33.75 ±0.077 (-17%)	28.33 ±0.056 (-30%)	26.49 ±0.54 (-35%)
σ_x^u	[MPa]	472 ±6	377 ±12 (-20%)	392 ±14 (-17%)	352 ±22 (-25%)	332 ±16 (-30%)
ϵ_x^u	[%]	1.28 ±0.04	1.19 ±0.03	1.23 ±0.07	1.25 ±0.10	1.20 ±0.05

Table 2: Tensile properties of quasi-isotropic laminates at 120°C depending on prior fire conditions

		Virgin	After fire exposure 35kW 2min
G_{12}	[GPa]	1.35 ±0.05	0.71 ±0.01 (-47%)
σ^u	[MPa]	159 ±4	79 ±1 (-50%)
ϵ_x^u	[%]	27.34 ±0.27	14.09 ±0.33

Table 3: Inplane shear properties of [(0/90)]₇ laminates depending on prior fire conditions

		Virgin	After fire exposure			
			20kW 2min	30kW 2min	40kW 2min	50kW 2min
σ_x^u	[MPa]	151 ±3	65 ±4 (-57%)	52 ±5 (-66%)	49 ±3 (-68%)	28 ±4 (-81%)

Table 4: Compressive properties of quasi-isotropic laminates depending on prior fire conditions

Compared to tensile loadings, the influence of prior fire exposure on compressive ultimate strength is more dramatic in the case of quasi-isotropic laminates. Indeed, the strength decreases by 60 to 80% depending on fire conditions. The alignment of fibers in reinforced composites has a large influence

on their compressive response [18,19]. In woven-ply laminates, the crimp region plays a significant role in controlling the onset of failure, mostly because of their non-planar interply structure (Fig. 3a), and the presence of matrix-rich areas at the crimp. In woven-ply laminates, localized bending at the crimps is found to cause fiber crushing and the onset of kink-band formation. Such bending is also amplified by the formation of voids resulting from the degradation of the PPS matrix in matrix-rich areas. In such misaligned and damaged meso-structures, highly deformed inclined bands develop naturally through a process of localization of plastic deformation following the limit load in the axial load-displacement response (Fig. 8). Thus, the compressive response of fire-damaged laminates appears to be elastic/ductile with a gradual failure.

Figure 8: Comparison of compressive responses of quasi-isotropic laminates at 120°C depending on fire conditions

4 CONCLUSIONS

From the fire performance standpoint, the basic idea of the present work was to find out whether it is relevant to replace thermosetting-based (Epoxy) composites by TP-based (PPS) composites for applications in nacelles of aircraft's engines, or not. The service temperature of these nacelles is 120°C, hence justifying to perform tests at $T > T_g$ for C/PPS.

The influence of fire exposure on the high-temperature residual tensile and compressive behaviors of carbon fibers woven-ply PPS has been investigated for heat fluxes ranging from 20 to 50 kW/m². A prior fire exposure appears to be more detrimental to compressive mechanical properties than to tensile ones, as the residual ultimate strengths decrease by 80% and 30% respectively at high heat flux. Although the PPS matrix behavior is highly ductile at a test temperature $T > T_g$, the degree of retention of mechanical properties is quite high in C/PPS laminates subjected to more or less severe prior fire conditions.

By means of SEM observations, it appears that melting and resolidification (during cooling) of the PPS matrix due to fire exposure modify both meso- and micro-structures. Indeed, once the melting temperature is reached (280°C) during fire exposure, the melted PPS matrix is redistributed within the carbon fibers network which ultimately maintains a partial cohesion, hence justifying that high-performance TP-based laminates maintain a high degree of retention of residual tensile properties. However, the thermal decomposition of the PPS matrix leaves intra- and inter-laminar voids which may act as preferential sites for delamination during tensile loading, and to plastic buckling during compressive loading.

The next step of this work will consist in applying combined thermal and mechanical loading to investigate a critical service situation.

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